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WEARABLE ELECTRONIC TEXTILES FOR THE DETECTION OF LONELINESS IN OLDER INDIVIDUALS

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Smart textile & wearable

EPSRC

Engineering and Physical Sciences
Research

UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS

Deloneliness: £315k to UoL, £1.5M; 05/2022-0/2025

Smart textile

- As Age UK noted in 2018, 1.4 million older people class themselves as often lonely, and it is estimated this will rise to 2 million people over the aged of 50 by 2025;
- A report from the UK's Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport suggests that the wellbeing, health and productivity cost of loneliness are approximately £2.5 billion per person-year.

Background – choice of sensors

Main symptoms that need monitoring

- Increased stress and anxiety levels
- Lack of activity, sedentary lifestyle
- Lack of communication with people
- Comfort eating/drinking
- Sleep problems
- Crying

Related Physiological signals

- Heart rate
- Breathing rate
- Activity indoors/outdoors
- Cortisol levels
- Glucose levels
- Body temperature

ECG (Heart Rate)

- Stress
- Crying
- Sleep deprivation

Temperature

- Stress
- Sleep deprivation

Respiration

- Walking
- Talking
- Sitting
- Relaxing
- Laughing

Galvanic Skin Response (GSR)

- Emotional arousal
- Stress
- Anxiety
- Depression

Cortisol

- Stress
- Sleep deprivation

Sensors of choice for monitoring these signals

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Integrated healthcare sensor – physiological signal monitoring

- ✓ ECG & EMG sensor
- ✓ Temperature sensor
- ✓ Respiration sensor
- ✓ Wireless data transmission
- ✓ Sensor data acquisition system

Structure of the sensor

Human body temperature sensor

Smart Textile temperature sensor

Commercial temperature sensor

ECG sensor

Smart ECG sensor

Materials

- Silver nanoparticle paste
- TPU film

Fabrication method

- Screen printing

ECG value from readout circuit for textile sensor

— Smart Textile sensor
— Commercial sensor

AD8233 commercial ECG sensor

ECG sensor results

Other ECG patterns

Respiratory sensor

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SEM image of the sensors

Cross-sectional view of the sensor

Top view of the silver nano-particles

Conclusion & Future work

- Smart textile temperature sensor compared with commercial ones
- Smart textile ECG sensor compared with commercial ones
- Different ECG pattern investigation
- Smart textile sensor investigation under different breathing rate
- Future experimental assessment on different physical movement and emotional activities

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